

ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF IMITATION INNOVATIONS IN SMALL BUSINESS AND THE FORECAST OF INNOVATION PRODUCT INDICATORS

Akram Ochilov

Academician of Turan Academy of Sciences, Doctor of Economics (DSc), Professor, Karshi State University;

Gulbakhor Erkaeva

Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor, Karshi State University;

Bakhodir Salimov

Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Tashkent State University of Economics;

Navruz Shamsutdiov

Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD);

Nargiza Ochilova

doctoral student, Karshi Engineering-Economics Institute

Abstract. *The article covers the issues of innovative product production in small business enterprises, innovation and innovation identification criteria, imitative innovation strategy, imitative innovation concept for small business, decision-making in imitative innovation strategy, use of imitative innovation in innovative product production. Total and forecast indicators of innovative product production in small business were analyzed, and according to the analysis, innovative product production in small business is effective compared to large business.*

Keywords: *small business, innovation, innovative product, innovation process, stages of the innovation process, imitative innovations, types of innovation, econometric model, forecast indicators, coefficient of determination, trend model.*

Introduction

Currently, the creation of new types of products and services, the development and introduction of new technology and management processes in small business enterprises remain the most important factors of the sustainable development of small business enterprises. Innovative activities are related to the improvement of the quality and competitiveness of products, economy of material and labor resources, increase of labor productivity and improvement of organization and management of enterprise activities.

The concept of "innovation" (in English - novelty) is considered as the final result of innovative activity, and it is expressed in a new or improved product sold on the market or as a new or improved technological process used in practice [7].

The concept of "innovation" is different from the concepts of "invention" and "discovery". Innovation is used in practice, discovery is a new scientific product that was not known before, invention includes new equipment, mechanisms, instruments, technology, equipment, etc., and they may or may not be used in practice. According to Schumpeter, they can be included in innovation if they are put into practice by the business [12].

The concept of "innovation" was proposed and systematized by the Austrian economist Jozef Schumpeter, and it is used in modern economics [14]. It is organized as follows:

1. Using new types of machines and technologies in the production process and providing the market with a new or improved product.
2. Mastering the production of goods with new features.
3. Use of new types of raw materials in economic activities.
4. Mastering new forms of production organization and management.
5. Formation of new goods, services and markets.

The main criteria for determining innovation are in the following order: scientific novelty, practical importance, feasibility and commercialization. "Innovation" means the processes of creating new or improved equipment, technology, goods, services, management methods and other innovations by small business entities, which, in turn, improve the quality and efficiency of production, management, commercial and other processes. It is understood that it will increase the competitiveness of its subjects, export potential and profit from trade.

Innovative activity - activities related to the creation, acquisition, distribution and use of innovations [15].

Innovative activity is a unique productive force that leads to the integration of science and technology, material production and business.

The purpose of the research is to prove that the use of imitative innovations in the production of innovative products in small business enterprises is an effective way according to the experience of foreign countries and to justify with the help of forecasting models that the production of innovative products in small businesses is effective compared to large businesses.

Research methodology

The work of local and foreign scientists was used in writing the article. Implementation of innovations requires two types of investment: in fixed capital and training of qualified specialists, i.e. human capital.

Investing in fixed capital is not suitable for all small business entities, it is characteristic of some financially strong small business enterprises that do not have many such opportunities, and only these strong enterprises can invest the necessary funds in scientific research.

Investing in human capital means investing in scientific research related to strengthening the scientific and management potential of the enterprise. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, highly qualified specialists work in universities, scientific research institutes and large companies. The innovative potential of technical staff working in small business cannot be considered high. Thus, it can be said that many small business entities have limited investment opportunities and innovation potential. Therefore, small business entities are interested in carrying out innovative research together with scientific research institutes and universities.

The process of entering the market of innovative technologies takes place in the following sequence: original innovations (radical innovations) and imitative innovations. In original innovation, a new product is created using a new technology. It is known that original innovations, first of all, require a large expenditure on scientific research; secondly, the development of a new product requires a long period of time, and thirdly, it is associated with great risk. If the result is not obtained, the company will face a big loss. Original innovations are carried out by large, financially strong companies. Imitative innovation is a process of successive improvement and improvement of one's product.

In the conditions of a market economy, any innovative activity should be profitable from a commercial point of view. A small business will benefit from an innovation if the use of the innovation is to reduce costs and maximize profits, or if it is a new product that is in demand and profitable in the market.

Using the method of correlation-regression analysis and trend models, the amount of innovative products produced by small businesses on the national scale was forecasted according to the factor of costs spent on the production of innovative products, the obtained results were analyzed using statistical methods.

Analysis of literature

In the works of A.V. Shavel [12] and G. Fedyasheva [9], the meaning of the concepts "Innovation", "Innovative activity" and "Innovative potential" and their role in the innovative development of the economy are revealed. Specific features of the development of innovative entrepreneurship in Russia, methods of researching innovative development, assessment of innovative potential, strategic development and state support in the works of E.V. Bulanova, N.S.Somenkova, G.B. Yagunova and Bakalagin [2] studied. The works of A.A. Chesnakov [10] covered methodological bases and methods of forecasting, bases of regression analysis, forecasting of socio-economic processes, and issues of forecasting and planning in small business. In the work of A.A. Kasimov [6], attention is paid to the issues of modeling and forecasting of the processes of increasing the efficiency of the regional industrial network.

Among local scientists, M. Burkhanov [5] studied the issues of evaluating the impact of innovative development on the competitiveness of enterprises, and U.V. Gafurov [1] studied the innovative potential of industrial enterprises and its indicators in the work of increasing the activity of small businesses to implement innovations.

In the researches of foreign scientists, Xu Huixuan [3] and Yan Dondong [11] highlighted the advantages of imitative innovation and the development of small and medium businesses based on imitative innovation in the People's Republic of China.

Analysis and results

Large US companies are world leaders in terms of scientific and technical potential. But according to statistics, the probability of their success is 5%¹.

When viewed in terms of applied research, 50% provides technical success, 30% commercial success and only 12% leads to profit².

It is known that many enterprises in developed countries use secondary innovation, that is, they pay attention to the modernization of existing innovative technology and equipment.

Compared with original innovation, imitative innovation is less complex, but it is more competitive in the market.

First, imitative innovation reduces the risk associated with the sale of goods in the market, because technologies whose products have been tested in the market are imitative innovations.

Second, because the result of the first innovation is available, it is easy to implement an imitative innovation, which represents its advantage.

In imitative innovation, a technology suitable for the market is selected, and then the

¹Ershova G.E., Iovleva O.V. Product and technological innovations and innovations: integration and the market. // Proceedings of USUE. 2012. No. 5. P. 5-11.

²Syuy Huizhuang. Analysis of the benefits of imitation innovation. Humanities and social sciences. 2012. No. 7.

innovation enterprise conducts its own research, and this research is free from risk and error.

Imitative innovation uses ready-made technology and does not require further research and development.

Currently, it is a difficult issue for small business enterprises in our country to conduct independent research. It is possible to improve one's product and make it competitive with the help of imitative innovation. The implementation of imitative innovation has a good effect on the improvement of the innovative technological process and the improvement of the primary innovation product.

Imitative innovation does not require large funds, reduces the cost of the product, and this, in turn, leads to quick adaptation of the product to market demand and satisfaction of consumer needs. Firms can achieve their own independent innovation through imitative innovation. Examples of this are Japan, China and South Korea. They bought the technologies of the USA and European countries, implemented innovative processes from the idea of improving the new technology to the production of new improved technology and products, and created their own competitive products. China has developed its own 5G mobile network based on 4G mobile network and is a leader in this regard. The Japanese company SONY produces thousands of new products per year (TV, refrigerator, vacuum cleaner, computer, etc.). Most of them differ little from the previous ones, but such imitative innovations and changes meet the needs of various groups of consumers and are in great demand.

Compared to large enterprises, the management system in small business enterprises is compact and ensures the efficient and diverted use of investment resources (gibko). In large enterprises, the hierarchy system is large, and decision-making and adaptation to changes are very slow.

Small business enterprises adapt to the market and direct their investment resources to promising goods and technologies. Such characteristics of small business enterprises ensure the successful implementation of imitative innovations³.

We see that imitative innovation has a number of advantages over independent innovation. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the use of imitative innovations can be considered an effective way for small business enterprises:

low investment volume and not too high technological requirements. High technological requirements are placed on original innovations and large investments have to be attracted. Small businesses don't have that option. Imitative innovation costs less than independent innovation. According to the Bank of Japan's long-term lending research, between 1955 and 1970, Japan spent \$3 billion on acquiring technology, then conducting research, and implementing the result, while the country that sold its technology spent \$100 billion on first-stage development, research, and testing alone. spent US dollars³;

The process of creating a new technology and product requires long-term accurate research, development and experimental testing. In addition, the company that develops original innovations has to work in a new segment to sell the product on the market, which requires a lot of expenses.

Imitative innovations allow small businesses to save time and gain market share and profits in a short period of time.

³Yang Dongdong, Yang Shiaoqin. Rational thinking imitating innovation of SMEs in China. Technological development of the enterprise. 2011. No. 12.

In an imitative innovation strategy, the first promising technology is selected. Here the market demand is studied with the help of experts. The company's possibilities to improve this technology are studied, and the raw material base is also analyzed. After that, the process of imitation technology begins (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Imitative innovation strategy

When studying the scientific and technical potential of a small business enterprise in the conditions of Uzbekistan, its connection with scientific research institutes, universities and other scientific centers is taken into account. Another important issue is the issue of supplying the product with raw materials. It should be clear where, from which company it will be purchased and in which market the product will be sold. When choosing a promising technology, the study of the patent market will not be without a purpose. When using imitative innovation, a number of advantages are achieved.

Typically, imitative innovation is used in existing technologies. Here, it is possible to avoid the risks and reduce the costs incurred in the previous stages.

In original innovation, a new product is created and sold in new markets, and this is where the enterprise faces uncertainty. Long-term research and changes in the market often lead to negative consequences for enterprises that develop original innovations. It can be seen that imitative innovations carried out in small business enterprises have a high probability of success.

In imitative innovations, market demand can be estimated in advance. In addition, many goods are sold in the market semi-finished, improving and changing them increases the possibility of using imitative innovation. When analyzing the market, by studying the positive and negative aspects of the product, the company can use imitative innovation to change it to meet the needs of consumers, and this will lead to more profit.

Imitation innovations stimulate the modernization of production in small business enterprises, increase the competitiveness of the product and the export potential of the enterprise. Therefore, imitative innovation not only improves the economic indicators of small business enterprises, but also leads to a positive change in its composition.

Small business imitative innovation enterprises improve advanced technologies and products with the help of imitative innovations, and gradually raise their economic, technical and management system to a new high level, and can become an advanced enterprise and become an enterprise that competes with its products in international markets.

The ultimate goal of small business enterprises is not to improve advanced technologies through imitative innovation, to increase the quality of the product, to get additional profit, but to achieve their own original innovations later. In the use of imitation innovations, the experience of small business enterprises in the production of innovative products and the qualification of personnel will increase, the fund will increase, and their cooperation with scientific research institutes, universities and other scientific centers and international scientific organizations will be strengthened.

As advantages of original innovations, the following can be said: creates a high-quality

brand product; produces a product that will have a high share in the market and ensures monopoly profit; increases the competitiveness of the enterprise in the international market and makes it resistant to various risks. The enterprise passes the period of imitative innovation and turns into an original innovative product manufacturer using the experience, knowledge and technical capabilities it has acquired. That is, imitative innovation gradually moves from strategic development to original innovation strategy. Japan, China and South Korea are classic examples.

In the 80s of the 20th century, technological development in many areas reached the level of the world's leading countries, and products became competitive in the world market. In the 1990s, technological development in Japan reached the level of the world's leading countries, and in the 1994s, it abandoned imitative innovation and began to develop without imitative innovation⁴. The period of imitative innovation continues in China (the creation of 5G communication and becoming a world leader in this regard), South Korea (the development of the electronic network) and other countries. The country of Uzbekistan can also be included in this. In our country, automobile, textile, metallurgical industry (Tashkent metallurgical plant was built on the basis of advanced Italian technology) and other industrial sectors operate on the basis of the technologies of leading companies in developed foreign countries. At the same time, the period of using imitative innovations in enterprises of these industries began.

It is known from the world experience that if any product is not modernized for 2-5 years, the competitiveness of the product will decrease and the demand for it will decrease. During the former USSR, in the 1960s, a modern car factory was built in Togliatti with the Italian company "Fiat", but the demand for Zhiguli cars fell behind modern modernization, and the factory went bankrupt.

At present, modern drip irrigation, hydroponic greenhouses from advanced foreign technology are used in the agriculture of our country. These new technologies must also be updated and changed. This renewal and change is done using imitative innovation. The problem is that the lack of qualified specialists makes it difficult to use imitative innovations in these areas.

The concept of imitative innovation (type of imitative innovation) for small business is based on the five main types of innovation of the economist Jozef Schumpeter. Figure 2.

⁴Nikonova Ya.I. Modern trends in the development of the innovation policy of economic systems. // Problems of accounting and finance. 2014. No. 1 (13). pp. 23-27.

Figure 2. Concept of imitative innovation for small business

1. Imitation of creating a new product or improving product quality. Usually, the value of the product of the primary innovation is high, and in the secondary innovation, by eliminating its shortcomings or making changes to it, it can find its place in the market by producing a product that satisfies consumer demand.

2. Simulating the use of new technology and new equipment. Here, some shortcomings of technology and equipment are eliminated or they are modernized. Of course, solving such issues requires funds and highly qualified specialist personnel. For example, a large company produces hand washing soap, but some of the soap packages do not contain soap. The technological line is not working well. The company spends a lot of money to eliminate this shortcoming. Another small business faced the same problem but lacked funds. The head of the company assigned the mechanic to fix this problem, he installed several coolers on the tape and solved the problem.

3. Imitation of entering and mastering new markets. Here, if the company's funds are not enough, it is possible to solve the problem by using the marketing method of modern, advanced companies, that is, by making changes to it and adapting it to itself.

4. Imitation of a new source of raw resources. It affects the quality and cost of raw materials. The price of quality raw materials is high. Low-quality raw materials affect the quality of the product. Here the company has to choose.

5. Imitation of the use of new organizations. The enterprise uses the experience of effectively operating enterprises, implements and improves it.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the introduction of patented advanced foreign technologies into production and their improvement through imitative innovations would lead to the acceleration of the innovative development of small business enterprises. But here it is appropriate to establish a policy of covering the costs of small business enterprises to a certain extent.

Small business enterprises create innovation in cooperation with other interested enterprises (scientific research centers also participate in this cooperation). The advantage of such cooperation is that the common interests and resources of the enterprises are united.

Currently, the type of cooperation of imitative innovations is widely popular in innovative activities.

The stages of using imitative innovations are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Decision making in imitative innovation strategy

1. Assessment of the internal capabilities of the enterprise and the external environment. In assessing the internal capabilities, first of all, one should have the ability to master and learn the technology and update it. One of the main conditions is to be able to organize the production process of a new product at the level of demand and to be able to start selling it. Therefore, before implementing the imitative innovation strategy, the enterprise should objectively assess its capabilities. Here, it is necessary to objectively assess the state of financial and technical equipment of the enterprise, personnel potential, employees' ability to use new technology and its imitative innovation, use of material and non-material resources. Here it is appropriate to use the opportunities of universities, research institutes, innovative technology park.

It is important for the company to have a clear idea of its strengths and weaknesses. Here it is appropriate to use the SWOT method.

2. When external factors are analyzed, the situation in the market, in which phase of the product's life cycle, assessment of growth, stable, decline phases (in the decline phase, imitation products are not expected to be released to the market), innovative activities of the state, policy of supporting KB, future partners, competitors, raw material supplier the issue of studying enterprises is important for the enterprise. Such studies prevent ineffective technology and product selection.

When choosing a simulated object, the necessary information should be obtained from all information sources. Having information about new technologies is the main way to choose an effective imitative innovation strategy. To obtain information about new technologies: pay close attention to new technologies for sale, developments and advertisements of international companies, study patent applications, study scientific research publications, participate in industry conferences and trade fairs, go to companies, check competitors' Internet it is necessary to look at the sites and so on. Keeping in touch with customers and sales agencies, both forward and backward communication is also important here.

It is always necessary to increase the level of knowledge of the employees of KB subjects engaged in imitative innovative activities about technologies and technology imitation, otherwise the increasing gap between the level of knowledge of employees and existing new technologies will have a negative effect on the final result. Strengthening of internal capabilities of the enterprise is the main factor of effective implementation of imitative innovations.

Simulation objective and simulation plan. In order for an imitation innovation product to be competitive, it is necessary to pay attention to the following: product appearance, technical indicators, quality and price. When an imitation object is selected, it is selected with a specific purpose. To achieve the set goal, you need to have a clear plan. Here, technical design, production equipment, costs, materials, marketing strategy, production period, staffing issues should find their expression. The plan may also include closing down existing production.

Property rights should also be considered when implementing imitative innovations. An imitation product is often associated with a patented technology.

Being the owner of the trademark and intellectual property of the company that produced the primary product. Here, it is important not to violate the framework of the legislation in action and to implement the imitation within the framework allowed by the legislation. But imitation production also needs protection.

It should be noted that the imitation product is different from the original product, the imitation product is inferior to the original product in terms of its technical indicators, which is related to the technological potential of the enterprise.

For example, Apple released its mobile phones and dramatically increased the market demand. Mobile phone manufacturers saw this and started selling a copy of the mobile phone. Despite the fact that the manufactured mobile phone was inferior to Apple phones in terms of quality, it started to make a profit. These mobile phones meet the fashion requirements of the appearance and the low price made them find their place in the market (China, South Korea).

The analysis of the activity of the innovative technology park "Yashnobad" in our country shows that the majority of the products developed in it are based on the use of imitation innovations. For example: production of 3D objects using plastic and photopolymers, production

of SIM cards and various other cards, production of drones, production of interactive robots, etc. These products already have existing production technologies, but the characteristics of these products are being improved through imitative innovation.

In general, the success of an imitation product depends on its marketability. If the innovative product brings profit and leads to the development of the enterprise, it is considered a successful innovation.

Thus, the quality and technical performance of the imitative product ensure product competitiveness, increase subsequent orders, and at the same time guarantee the success of the imitative innovation strategy.

Industries that use imitative innovations: products of high and medium high-tech industries: high-tech industries include aircraft construction, computer and pharmaceutical industries; automobile production, electrical equipment and chemical industry to medium-high technological industries; rubber and plastic production, metallurgy and metal processing, shipbuilding industries to medium low technological industries; low-tech industries include the food industry, textile, clothing, and footwear industries.

Table 1 shows the dynamics of information on the total innovative product produced by all enterprises in our country and the amount of innovative product produced by KB enterprises on their own and the costs of their production.

Table 1

Information on the total and only the innovative products produced by small business enterprises and the costs of their production (billion soums)

	Total volume of produced innovative products and services (Y)	Expenditure on total produced innovative products and services (X)	Produced by small businesses volume of innovative products and services (Y')	Produced by small businesses expenditure on innovative products and services (X')
2010	1 849,0	264,4	113,2	40,6
2011	1 348,7	372,6	116,1	32,3
2012	3 635,9	311,9	265,4	47,3
2013	4 614,7	4 634,2	409,8	181,2
2014	7 043,0	3 757,4	1 160,7	351,4
2015	8 023,6	5 528,3	1 681,8	354,8
2016	10 688,2	2 571,4	1 671,9	211,4
2017	18 543,3	4 162,3	2 324,3	715,3
2018	28 871,5	4 707,2	7 196,3	1 156,8
2019	26 811,4	6 603,5	8 455,4	1 939,9
2020	31 142,8	6 830,0	14 129,1	1 041,6

Source: Prepared based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Volume of innovative products and services produced in total (Y), expenditure on innovative products and services produced in total (X), volume of innovative products and services produced by small business enterprises (Y') and innovative products and services produced by small business enterprises Based on linear trend regression (1), (2), (3), (4) models for expenditure (X') indicators, forecast values for 2021-2024 were developed, Table 2.

The trend model of the volume (Y) of the total produced innovative products and services:

$$y = 3232,1 t - 6431,4 \quad (R = 0,8934) \quad (1)$$

The trend model of expenditure (X) on total manufactured innovative products and services:

$$x = 625,52t - 140,09 \quad (R = 0,7268) \quad (2)$$

The trend model of the volume (Y') of innovative products and services produced by small business enterprises:

$$y' = 1168,8t - 3601,6 \quad (R = 0,7241) \quad (3)$$

Trend model of expenditures (X') on innovative products and services produced by small business enterprises:

$$x' = 153,56t - 369,35 \quad (R = 0,7054) \quad (4)$$

Table 2

Forecast indicators of the volume of innovative products and services produced by total and small business enterprises (billion soums)

	Total volume of produced innovative products and services (Y)	Expenditure on total produced innovative products and services (X)	Volume of innovative products and services produced by small business enterprises (Y')	Expenditure on innovative products and services produced by small business enterprises (X')
2021	32 353,8	7 366,2	10 424,0	1 473,4
2022	35 585,9	7 991,7	11 592,8	1 626,9
2023	38 818,0	8 617,2	12 761,6	1 780,5
2024	42 050,1	9 242,7	13 930,4	1 934,1

Figure 4 shows the graphs of forecast indicators. It can be seen from the graph that the forecast indicators of the volume of innovative products and services produced in total have an upward trend. By 2024, this indicator will be 10.9 trillion compared to 2020. increases to soums and 42.1 trillion. amounts to soums, in terms

Figure 4. Graph of forecast indicators of the volume of innovative products and services produced by total and small business enterprises (billion soums).

of percentage, this indicator increases by 35.0%. Forecast indicators of the volume of innovative

products and services produced by small business enterprises also have a tendency to increase during the forecast period. However, by 2024, this indicator will decrease by 198.7 billion soums compared to 2020, and by 13.9 trillion. amounts to soums, this indicator is 99.0 percent.

Figure 5. Graph of total production and expenditure on innovative products and services produced by small business enterprises (billion soums)

If we analyze the graph of total production and expenditure on innovative products and services produced by small business enterprises (Figure 5), we see that expenditure will increase during the forecast period. We see that spending on total manufactured innovative products and services increased by 35.3% in 2024 compared to 2020. Growth in spending over the forecast period (35.3%) is slightly higher than the growth rate of innovative products and services (35.0). Spending on innovative products and services produced by small businesses also increased during this forecast period and amounted to 185.7%, while the increase in the volume of innovative products and services was equal to 99% during this period. We see that the production of innovative products and services is associated with high costs.

When we look at the volume of innovative products and services produced by small business enterprises (Figure 3), this indicator was higher than the total innovative product produced in 7 out of 10 years considered by small businesses. This advantage in small business is maintained during the forecast period. In 2020, this difference is at the maximum level and it is 13.57-4.56=9.1 billion. amounted to 7.20-4.55=2.65 billion soums by 2024. In the production of total innovative products and services, the cost per unit of innovative product is higher than that of small businesses.

Figure 6. Total volume of innovative products and services produced by small business enterprises (billion soums) per unit cost (1 billion soums)

Thus, to conclude, we can see that the innovative output per unit cost in small business enterprises is higher than the total innovative output per unit cost, and this can be considered as a motivating factor for small business to engage in innovative activities.

Conclusions and suggestions

Successive use of imitative innovations in small business enterprises leads to a strong change in the composition of enterprises. The economic, technical and organizational changes taking place in the enterprise raise it to a higher stage of development. The enterprise can start producing its original innovations after passing through the stage of imitative innovation.

Small business enterprises purchase advanced foreign technology and use imitative innovation to further improve the characteristics of this technology. This leads to savings on development costs and market research costs, reducing investment risks;

Foreign drip irrigation technologies and hydroponics and other greenhouses, which are effectively used in agriculture, require improvement over time with the help of imitative innovations based on scientific and technical achievements, such as "SMART AGRICULTURE". The transition of small business enterprises from imitative innovations to their own innovations at the next stage can be considered as the main production factor that ensures the innovative development of our country.

it can be seen from the graphs above that the volume of innovative products and services produced in total and produced by small business enterprises has a tendency to increase during the forecast period, but at the same time, we see that the growth rate of innovative products over the years is higher than the growth rate of costs, especially in small businesses;

in the forecast period, it can be observed that the volume of innovative products and services produced at the expense of one unit cost (1 billion soums) is much higher in small business enterprises than the total produced innovative product, which means that small business has an advantage over large business in creating innovative products, and innovative development in small business is imitative development with the help of innovations can be considered an effective way.

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